

Visualising Bibliographical Data on Polish Literature after 1989

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Goal

This paper discusses the challenges of meaningful exploration and visualisation of the large networks based on bibliographical data. The particular focus is put on tracing relationships between the actors of literary life and providing data-stories of career trajectories and success/failure patterns of particular writers.

Data

The analysis is conducted on the data derived from Polish Literary Bibliography (PBL) and ingested into neo4j environment. PBL is a comprehensive database of Polish literary and cultural life, indexing all instances of literary life and literary reception: books, reviews, journal articles, mentions in newspapers, dramas, adaptations of literary works, and literary prizes. This provides rich data about the relationships between literary entities (e.g. A is a review of B; C is an adaptation of D). The dataset extracted from the PBL for this study provides a network of over 2 million unweighted connections between over 1 million nodes in a timespan of 1989-2002 (see: Table 1. for breakdown and Fig. 1 for data model visualisation).

NODES	1072066	EDGES	2080536
Book	201309	Published	871285
Journal	2814	Located in	213420
Journal article	673907	Is about	231843
Location	3634	Awarded	6215
Person	153215	Wrote	757773
Prize	3616		
Publisher	33571		

Table 1. Breakdown of nodes and edges in the dataset

Method

In the presentation I am focusing on the challenges with meaningful visualisation of the large dataset by providing a comparison between a mono-modal projection of inter-author relationships based on the literary reception (edges created through books and articles written about the author) with career trajectories derived from multimodal dataset in neo4j. The differences will be discussed on the basis of career trajectories of writers who debuted after 1989: on the one hand I will employ network statistics and visualisation of tendencies overtime on the monomodal projection of the dataset in Gephi) on the other, I will use more advanced and qualitative queries to reveal overall patterns and outliers in data (with Neo4j GDS).

The analyses currently carried out in the framework of CLS INFRA TNA fellowship are aimed at plotting individual career patterns of authors and how subsequent events (e.g. publishing a book with a large publisher, being reviewed in a particular journal, receiving a prize) influence their careers.

Figure 1. Data model.

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